

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

Comparison of ice-only to coupled ice-ocean simulations

Deliverable D4.3

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1. Publishable summary

As the climate warms, melting ice from the Antarctic Ice Sheet will raise sea levels in many regions on Earth. But predicting exactly how much remains a big challenge. To improve these predictions, researchers run numerous computer simulations of the Antarctic Ice Sheet, accounting for how warm ocean water melts ice from below. This is computationally expensive and time-consuming, so scientists often use simplified approximations rather than full, detailed ocean models. This deliverable tests how reliable those approximations really are. The team calibrated two types of models against twenty years of satellite observations: a faster "ice-only" model using simplified ocean melt equations, and a slower but more realistic "coupled" model that simulates the ice and ocean together. Both setups were used to simulate ice-sheet mass loss to 2300. Ongoing comparisons between the two approaches will reveal whether the simpler, faster method is sufficiently trustworthy to predict Antarctica's contribution to sea level rise in the centuries ahead.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Introduction

To obtain robust uncertainty estimates for future freshwater fluxes from the Antarctic Ice Sheet, a large ensemble of ice-sheet simulations is typically required to sample uncertainties in model parameters, physical processes, and climate forcings. This approach presents two major computational challenges. First, overcoming well-known numerical limitations in ice-sheet modelling demands sufficiently high spatial resolution. Second, accurately representing the complex two-way interactions between the ice sheet and the adjacent ocean and atmosphere over relevant length scales and timescales requires computationally expensive, high-fidelity three-dimensional general circulation models (GCMs).

The first challenge has been addressed in several ice-sheet models using irregular and adaptive grid techniques, which allow resolution to be concentrated in dynamically important regions. In addition, deploying these models on high-performance computing (HPC) systems enables a substantial increase in the number of simulations that can be run simultaneously. The results presented here have made use of both advances.

The second challenge is commonly addressed by replacing computationally intensive GCMs with more efficient parameterisations of key processes, such as ice-shelf basal melt and surface mass balance. However, it remains unclear to what extent these simplified parameterisations can reliably reproduce the behaviour of fully coupled 3D simulations, and the associated uncertainties have yet to be quantified. Addressing this gap for ice-shelf basal melt is the primary objective of deliverable D4.3.

The work in this deliverable is organised into 4 parts, each detailed in the sections below.

1. Ice-dynamics calibration: A new, computationally efficient method was developed to calibrate uncertain ice-dynamics parameters in large-scale viscous ice-flow models. The approach places strong constraints on the ice rheology and sliding law, but does not lead to (or indeed, require) knowledge about external forcing parameters related to ice-shelf basal melt. These are calibrated separately in the next step.

2. Calibration of ice-shelf melt in ice-only simulations: Using the calibrated ice-dynamics parameters, we generated an ensemble of approximately 750 high-resolution, circum-Antarctic ice-sheet model hindcast simulations covering the period 2000 to 2020. The ensemble samples a broad range of basal melt parameterisations and associated parameters commonly used in the literature. Using Bayesian inference techniques, we inferred, for the first time, a posterior distribution of melt parameters constrained by spatially resolved observations of both basal melt and changes in ice-sheet dynamics.

3. Calibration of ice-shelf melt in coupled ice-ocean simulations: An analogous calibration was performed for uncertain melt parameters within a fully coupled ice-ocean configuration of the Amundsen Sea. This was made possible by a first-of-its-kind ensemble of high-resolution coupled ice-ocean hindcast simulations and a comprehensive dataset of basal melt and ice-dynamics observations.

4. Comparison between ice-only and coupled ice-ocean simulations: In ongoing work, projected future freshwater fluxes for the Amundsen Sea up to 2300 are being compared between the calibrated ice-only (step 2) and coupled ice-ocean (step 3) models across a range of future climate scenarios. All results are being reported in a series of peer-reviewed papers, currently either submitted or in preparation, see Section 2.3.2.1.2 Ice dynamics calibration.

Partner UNN has been working with the open-source ice-sheet model Úa (<https://github.com/GHilmarG/UaSource/wiki>) to develop a new methodology to calibrate ice-flow physics against comprehensive remote-sensing data on ice geometry and velocity from 2000 to 2020. The method employs large-ensemble simulations to train an ice-flow emulator and enables estimation of the posterior distribution of uncertain model parameters using Bayesian inference and a computationally inexpensive Markov Chain Monte Carlo method. The so-called ‘diagnostic calibration’ has provided valuable insights into the likely distribution of uncertain model parameters, such as the ice rheology and form of the sliding law, as shown in Fig. 1. Results were submitted for publication to the Journal of Glaciology, and a preprint is publicly available online (De Rydt, 2025).

Fig.1: Key results from the diagnostic calibration of ice-flow dynamics in West Antarctica. (a) Panels along the diagonal show prior and posterior distributions for the uncertain model parameters, based on concurrent observations of ice geometry and surface velocity changes in West Antarctica across three observational epochs (2000–2009, 2000–2014, and 2000–2020) and assuming zero model discrepancy. The posterior assigns zero probability to the hybrid sliding law, so only power-law sliding law distributions are shown. Orange dots represent parameter combinations used to train the surrogate models. (b-d) Discrepancy between observed changes in surface velocity and simulated values, averaged over 10 randomly sampled parameter sets within the posterior 95% credible region (black dots in panel (a)), shown for each epoch and a subset of the model domain.

2.1.2 Ice-shelf basal melt calibration in ice-only simulations

The calibrated ice-flow model was configured in a high-resolution circum-Antarctic setup (see Fig.2), and an ensemble of approximately 750 hindcast simulations (years 2000–2020) was run to assess the sensitivity of the ice dynamics evolution to different ice-shelf basal melt parameterisations. A new mean ocean state data product from OCEAN ICE WP1 was used to drive the basal melt simulations.

Fig 2: Unstructured mesh of a circum-Antarctic configuration of the Úa ice-flow. Local refinement down to 1.5 km can be seen in areas of fast flow, high shear and near the grounding line. Floating ice-shelves are masked in blue.

Simulated changes in Antarctic-wide ice thickness and velocity were evaluated against spatially resolved observational records of ice thickness and velocity change, thereby allowing the likelihood distribution of basal melt parameterisations and associated parameters to be estimated (see Fig. 3 for a preliminary example). This approach offers a novel and powerful alternative to the more commonly applied method of evaluating static basal melt patterns against inherently uncertain satellite-derived melt maps. Optimising model parameters against a 20-year record of observed ice-sheet dynamics, rather than relying on a snapshot of uncertain melt estimates, ensures that present-day ice-sheet behaviour is captured more accurately. It also leads to increased confidence in future projections.

Results are being prepared for publication in an open-access journal.

Fig. 3: Preliminary example of Bayesian calibration of basal melt parameterisations and associated parameters against observations of speed change -du- (top left panel) and basal melt rates -ab- (not shown). Only calibrating against -du- yields a modelled velocity response shown in the second panel on the top, with a posterior distribution of the uncertain parameter in the local quadratic melt parameterisation shown by the blue curve in the bottom panel. Only calibrating against -ab- yields a modelled velocity response shown in the third panel on the top, with optimal parameters for the local quadratic melt parameterisation shown by the red dashed curve in the bottom panel. Calibrating against both -du- and -ab- yields the velocity response in the fourth panel on the top, with a posterior distribution of the model parameters shown by the green dotted curve.

2.1.3 Basal melt calibration in a coupled ice-ocean model

UNN has set up a new configuration of the coupled ice-sheet-ocean model \acute{U} aMITgcm (<https://github.com/knaughten/UaMITgcm>) for the Amundsen Sea, with a greatly improved representation of the regional oceanography (based on Naughten et al. (2023)), and a high-resolution ice-sheet configuration initialised with the latest available datasets. The coupled model was calibrated using an ensemble of simulations constrained by spatial observations of basal melt rates and changes in ice speed and thickness over a historical period. This represents the first calibration that jointly incorporates oceanic and glaciological observations for optimising melt-rate parameters in a fully coupled ice-ocean model.

Key results for the calibration are shown in Figure 4. To match historical observations of ice dynamical changes, the transient-coupled calibration favours parameter values that enhance basal melt near deep grounding lines ($H_{\text{Trans}} > 0\text{m}$ in Fig.4), highlighting the sensitivity of ice dynamics to localised ocean forcing. Further details are provided in a preprint (Reed et al., 2026), which was submitted for publication in *The Cryosphere*.

Fig.4: Likelihood scores for 68 coupled ice sheet-ocean model parameter combinations, calculated using observations of basal melt, changes in ice thickness and velocity and their associated errors. Three uncertain parameters were tested: the drag coefficient in the MITgcm ocean model (C_d on the x-axis), a constant heat exchange coefficient (γ_{T0} on the y-axis), which is used in areas near the grounding line where the water column thickness is less than H_{Trans} (panels).

2.1.4 Comparison of ice-only and coupled ice-ocean simulations and ongoing work

Following calibration of the ice-only model (2.1.2, 2.1.3) and the coupled ice-ocean model (2.1.4) over the historical period, both models are extended into the future to project and compare Antarctic freshwater flux estimates across a range of climate forcing scenarios.

For the circum-Antarctic ice-only setup, the combined posterior distribution of ice dynamics and basal melt parameterisations was sampled to construct a set of optimal model configurations as starting points for future simulations. Anomalies in ocean and atmospheric conditions from two CMIP6 models (UKESM and CESM2) were calculated to inform future estimates of basal melt and surface mass balance for the SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios through 2300. Simulations are currently underway and will be submitted for publication by the end of the OCEAN ICE project.

For the top-scoring coupled ice-ocean simulation (green box in Fig. 4), simulations were extended to the year 2100, forced by bias-corrected CESM2 ocean conditions under an SSP5-8.5 scenario (Naughten et al., 2023). The simulated sea-level changes alongside estimates for uncalibrated and present-day ocean conditions are shown in Figure 5 and were submitted for publication (Reed et al., 2026).

Fig.5: Change in volume above floatation (converted to mass, Gt) and the corresponding cumulative sea-level contribution for (blue) default ocean-melt parameters and present-day control forcing, (red) default ocean-melt parameters and SSP5-8.5 forcing, (green) new transient-calibrated parameters and present-day control forcing, and (magenta) new transient-calibrated parameters and SSP5-8.5 forcing. In the inset, all simulations are compared against observations from Davison et al. (2023b) for the hindcast period (2013–2017). Also highlighted are the best (solid green) and worst (dashed orange) five scoring simulations in the transient calibration. Dots are shown at the end to illustrate the range of modelled and observed sea-level contribution values in 2017.

The coupled ice-ocean results have two main limitations:

- 1) They rely on a single realisation of the ice-dynamics parameters in the ice sheet model, thereby preventing any assessment of how ice-sheet parametric and structural uncertainty contribute to future sea-level projections.
- 2) They do not extend beyond 2100, and therefore offer no insight into the multi-century evolution of the ice sheet, which has been shown to exhibit strongly non-linear and potentially irreversible behaviour (Seroussi et al. 2024).

To address both shortcomings, and in parallel with the approach taken for the ice-only simulations (Section 2.1.3), the historical calibration and future projections of the coupled ice-ocean simulations are being extended to incorporate a range of historically calibrated ice-dynamics parameters (addressing the first limitation), and simulations will be extended out to reach 2300 (addressing the second limitation).

Once future simulations from the ice-only and coupled ice-ocean simulations are finalised, a comprehensive comparison between the two approaches will provide valuable insights into the validity of simple melt parameterisations for simulating the complex ice-ocean interactions in the Amundsen Sea over the next decades to centuries. The results will be prepared for submission to a peer-reviewed journal.

Alongside the work on comparing ice-only to coupled ice-ocean simulations for the Amundsen Sea, progress is also being made on a ÚaMITgcm configuration of the Weddell Sea. This configuration has previously been

used to simulate the ocean and ice-sheet response to high-end CO₂ emission scenarios over the next 1.5 centuries (Naughten et al. 2021). These simulations have recently been extended by a further 1.5 centuries, and a range of reversibility experiments have been conducted to assess the possibility and timescales for a reversal to cold-cavity conditions following a transition to warm-ocean conditions in a high-end emission scenario. This work has been accepted for publication in the *Journal of Geophysical Research - Oceans* (Reese et al., 2026). In the meantime, comprehensive studies of the Weddell Sea response to future climate change for a range of uncertain ice-sheet model parameters (Hill et al., 2021), and reversibility experiments (Hill et al., 2024) have been conducted with the ice-only model *Úa*, outside the OCEAN ICE project. Preliminary analysis suggests a qualitatively similar long-term response between coupled ice-ocean models and ice-only simulations.

2.2 References

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- J. De Rydt, Basal sliding and ice rheology in West Antarctica constrained by multi-epoch satellite observations, submitted to *Journal of Glaciology*, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.176894749.90399034/v1>
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- R. Reese, J. De Rydt, K.A. Naughten, Ice-Sheet-Ocean Interactions and the Reversibility of a Regime Shift Beneath Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf. *Journal of Geophysical Research - Oceans*, [accepted], 2026
- H. Seroussi, T. Pelle, W. H. Lipscomb, A. Abe-Ouchi, T. Albrecht, J. Alvarez-Solas *et al.* Evolution of the Antarctic Ice Sheet over the next three centuries from an ISMIP6 model ensemble. *Earth's Future*, **12**, e2024EF004561, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024EF004561>

2.3 Open Science

The work summarised in this deliverable has contributed to several peer-reviewed publications:

- De Rydt J., Basal sliding and ice rheology in West Antarctica constrained by multi-epoch satellite observations, submitted to a gold open access journal (Journal of Glaciology) and uploaded to a **preprint server** (<https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.176894749.90399034/v1>)
- B. Reed, J. De Rydt, K.A. Naughten, D.N. Goldberg, Calibration of a coupled ice sheet-ocean model using observations of ice dynamics and basal melt in West Antarctica, submitted to an open-access journal (The Cryosphere) and available on the EGU sphere **preprint** server (<https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2026-931>)
- Qing Q., J. De Rydt, V. Coulon, F. Pattyn, Ice dynamics as essential constraints on ice-shelf basal melt parameterisations, *in preparation* for The Cryosphere
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3. Results

The main results from D4.3 are summarised as follows.

A new methodology was developed to calibrate ice-flow physics in the Antarctic Ice Sheet model Úa against spatially and temporally resolved remote-sensing observations of changes in ice speed and thickness from 2000 to 2020, yielding constrained posterior distributions for key parameters, including ice rheology and the sliding law. Building on this, an ensemble of high-resolution circum-Antarctic hindcast simulations was run to calibrate ice-shelf basal melt parameterisations against spatially resolved observations of both melt rates and changes in ice-sheet dynamics, providing stronger constraints than the commonly used approach of comparing against uncertain satellite-derived melt snapshots. An analogous calibration was also performed for the first time within a fully coupled ice-ocean model of the Amundsen Sea, jointly incorporating oceanic and glaciological observations to optimise melt-rate parameters.

Looking ahead, both the historically calibrated ice-only and coupled ice-ocean models are being extended to project Antarctic freshwater fluxes to 2300 under multiple climate scenarios. Initial coupled model projections to 2100 show that calibrated parameters, which favour enhanced basal melt near deep grounding lines, produce meaningfully different sea-level contributions compared to default, uncalibrated configurations. Ongoing work will directly compare ice-only and coupled ice-ocean projections, offering critical insight into how well simplified melt parameterisations can reproduce the complex ice-ocean interactions that govern Antarctic sea-level change over the coming centuries.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following project objectives as described in the description of the action.

O2: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models, using historical observations and new data sets obtained in the project.

A new approach to computing ice-shelf basal melt was developed and calibrated within the coupled ice-ocean model ÚaMITgcm. The method assumes that in thin, under-resolved water columns, melt rates

scale linearly with thermal driving and are independent of the mixed-layer friction velocity. This introduces a set of physically interpretable parameters that modulate melt rates in the vicinity of the deep grounding line. Comprehensive calibration against available satellite observations revealed that the default basal melt formulation used in many ocean models fails to reproduce observed changes in ice-sheet thickness and flow speed. The calibrated scheme instead favours elevated melt rates near the grounding line, a feature that proves essential for capturing the observed ice-dynamic evolution over the historical period. All code developments will be made available through public repositories upon publication (Reed et al., 2026)

O3: Improve representation of AIS dynamics and integrate this knowledge into ice sheet and coupled ice sheet-climate models.

Observational datasets have played a central role at every stage of this work, underpinning both model initialisation and calibration. This led to a substantially improved representation of uncertain ice-flow physics (including ice rheology and basal sliding) as well as the calculation of ice-shelf basal melt. All findings will be made available to the community through open-access publications.

O4: Quantify AIS melt sensitivity to climate forcing and reduce the ‘deep uncertainty’ in freshwater flux and SLR projections to 2300.

By combining the newly developed and calibrated Amundsen Sea configuration of the coupled ice-sheet–ocean model *ÚaMITgcm* with historically calibrated ice-only simulations using *Úa*, important insights will be gained into the validity of commonly used basal melt parameterisations. Bringing both approaches together within a unified framework will allow uncertainty bounds for the ice-only simulations to be derived, providing more reliable estimates of uncertainty in sea-level rise and freshwater projections associated with simplified basal melt parameterisations, relative to those from more sophisticated coupled ice-ocean models.